

HAURÉLIO, Marco. **Bafafá na arca de Noé**. Illustrations Anabella López. São Paulo: DCL, 2017.

REVIEW¹

Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro²

Marco Haurélio is a writer, professor and researcher of cordel (string literature) and Brazilian folklore. He was a Jabuti Prize finalist and winner of the Cordel Literature Culture Prize, of the Ministry of Culture. *Bafafá na Arca de Noé* (Brouhaha in Noah's Ark) is developed around the biblical story of Noah's Ark, but does so through rhyming and humorous illustrations close to the infantile trait. It recovers some legends about the characteristics of the animals: why is the flamingo bow-legged; why does the giraffe have a long neck; and why does the armadillo dig the floor?.

Keywords: Twine. Folklore. Legends.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2018 Bologna. Books published in 2017 and reviewed in 2018. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

² Voter.